

Social Case Work Is an Important Component in Social Work: A Review

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Abstract:

Social casework is one of the primary methods of working with individuals in human welfare organizations to help clients cope more efficiently with their problems in the context of their social functioning. It enables individuals to deal with their problems in a systematic manner based on the knowledge of human behaviour and various other tested approaches. It helps in developing more satisfying relations within their environment. Social casework as a method of social work has emerged from the time of industrialization and its concomitant urbanization. It is the offspring of charity organization societies movement which was introduced in late 1870s. In this unit you should be able to understand the social and psychological explanation of human behaviour, role of casework in managing problems of persons in modern society and how casework is perceived by the practitioners in India.

Key Words: *Social Work, Case Study, Practice, Methods*

Introduction

Social casework practitioners in India view the concepts of casework differently. According to them, social casework can be practiced successfully in a democratic society only. In the context of social casework practice, democracy implies freedom and self-fulfillment. In the Indian context the concept of self fulfillment and self expression go hand in hand with the concept of conformity to the group norm. It is believed that an individual does not have a right to express himself/herself, to decide upon an action he/she will like to undertake or which he/she is capable of undertaking. In Indian society the individual remains, more or less, a participating member bound to his/her original group. His/her group teaches him/her how he/ she should restrain himself/herself and what characteristics he/she should suppress in order to be acceptable to other members. He/she can be rejected or ridiculed by his/her group if he/she does not conform to the social norms. In other words, in Indian context, the client will not have the right to individualism or the right to self determination

Methodology

The research paper is based on secondary data. The data is taken from different research reports, journals, websites and research papers, Magazine and daily Newspapers, and other Educational text books

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the concept of Social Work
2. To understand the concept Social Case Work
3. To understand the Components and Principles Social Case Work

What is Social Work?

Social work is an academic discipline and practice-based profession concerned with meeting the basic needs of individuals, families, groups, communities, and society as a whole to enhance their individual and collective well-being. Social work practice draws from areas, such as psychology,

sociology, health, political science, community development, law, and economics to engage with systems and policies, conduct assessments, develop interventions, and enhance social functioning and responsibility. The ultimate goals of social work include the improvement of people's lives, alleviation of biopsychosocial concerns, empowerment of individuals and communities, and the achievement of social justice. Social work practice is often divided into three levels. Micro-work involves working directly with individuals and families, such as providing individual counselling/therapy or assisting a family in accessing services. Mezzo-work involves working with groups and communities, such as conducting group therapy or providing services for community agencies. Macro-work involves fostering change on a larger scale through advocacy, social policy, research development, non-profit and public service administration, or working with government agencies. Starting in the 1960s, a few universities began social work management programmes, to prepare students for the management of social and human service organizations, in addition to classical social work education.

Global Definition of the Social Work

“Social work is a practice-based profession and an academic discipline that promotes social change and development, social cohesion, and the empowerment and liberation of people. Principles of social justice, human rights, collective responsibility and respect for diversities are central to social work. Underpinned by theories of social work, social sciences, humanities and indigenous knowledge's, social work engages people and structures to address life challenges and enhance wellbeing. The above definition may be amplified at national and/or regional levels.”

Social Work methods

The methods of social work will help his/her to understand ways of helping people. Social work methods are:

Primary methods (direct helping method)

- 1) Social casework
- 2) Social group work.
- 3) Community organization.

Secondary methods (Auxiliary methods)

- 4) Social work research.
- 5) Social welfare administration.
- 6) Social Action

These six social work methods are systematic and planned ways of helping people.

1. **Social casework** deals with individual problems- individual in the total environment or as a part of it. An individual is involved in the problem as he is unable to deal with it on his own, because of reasons beyond his control. His anxiety sometimes temporarily makes him incapable of solving it. In any case, his social functioning is disturbed. The caseworker gets information regarding the client's total environment, finds out the causes, prepares a treatment plan and with a professional relationship tries to bring about a change in the perception and attitudes of the client.
2. **Social group work** is a social work service in which a professionally qualified person helps individuals through group experience so as to help them move towards improved relationships and social functioning. In group work individuals are important and they are helped to improve their social relationships, with flexible programs, giving importance to the personality development of the individual in group functioning and relationships. The group is the medium and through it and in it, individuals are helped to make necessary changes and adjustments.
3. **Community Organisation** is another method of social work. Being made up of groups, a community means organized systems of relationships but in reality, no community is perfectly organized. Community Organisation is a process by which a systematic attempt is made to improve relationships in a community. Identifying the problems, finding out resources for solving community problems, developing social relationships, and necessary programmes to realize the objectives of the community are all involved in community organization. In this way, the community can become self-reliant and develop a co-operative attitude among its members.
4. **Social Welfare Administration** is a process through which social work services both private and public, are organized and administered.

Developing programmes, mobilizing resources, involving selection and recruitment of personnel, proper organization, coordination, providing skillful and sympathetic leadership, guidance and supervision of the staff, dealing with financing and budgeting of the programmes and evaluation are, some of the functions of a social worker in administration.

5. **Social work research** is a systematic investigation for finding out new facts, test old hypotheses, verify existing theories, and discover causal relationships of the problems in which the social worker is interested. In order to scientifically initiate any kind of social work program, a systematic study of the given situation is necessary, through social work research and surveys.
6. **Social action** aims at bringing about desirable changes to ensure social progress. Creating awareness about social problems, mobilizing resources, encouraging different 'sections of people to raise their voice against undesirable practices, and also creating pressure to bring about the legislation are some of the activities of the social workers using the method of social action. It seeks to achieve a proper balance between community needs and solutions mainly through individual and group initiatives and self-help activities

Concept of Social Casework (Working with individuals)

Social case work is a unique method of problem-solving. It helps an individual to solve his psycho-social problems. Here the social worker is concerned with individual problems only. Here interventions come at the individual level. Professionally trained Social Worker helps a client with particular problems. Social case work is a primary method of social work. It is concerned with the adjustment and development of the individual towards more satisfying human relationship According to Bowers, "Social casework is an art in which knowledge of the science of human relations and skills in human relationships are used to mobilise capacities in the individual and resources in the community, appropriate to better adjustment between the client and all or any part of his total environment." In social case work a person with a problem comes to a place/agency where a professionally trained worker helps him through a given process. Social case work has four components-person, problem, place and process.

Various Social Scientists have tried to define social casework. In order to understand what social casework is, it appears essential to present some important social casework definitions given from time to time: - "Social case work consists of those processes which develop personality through

adjustments consciously effected, individual by individual, between men and their social environment". Most preferred social casework definition of her is: "Social case work may be defined as the art of doing different things for and with different people by cooperating with them to achieve at one and the same time their own and society's betterment".

Definitions

Mary Richmond (1917) Social casework is an art in which knowledge of the science of human relation, and skills in a relationship are used to mobilize capacity in individual and resources in the community appropriate for the better adjustment between the client and all or way part of his total environment.

Bowers (1949) "A process used by certain human welfare agencies to help individuals to cope more effectively with their problems in social functioning."

Perlman (1957) Social casework is a method employed by a social worker to help the individual find the solution to a problem of social adjustment which they are unable to handle in a satisfactory way by their own effort.

Hollies (1957) Social casework is the art of untangling and reconstructing the twisted personality in such a manner that the individual can adjust himself to his environment.

Jarrett (1919) Social casework means social treatment of maladjusted individuals involving an attempt to understand his personality behavior, and social relationship, and to assist him in working out a better social and personal adjustment.

Taft (1920) social casework which is both a tool and area of work consists of processes which develop personality through adjustment, consciously affect individual by individual between man and his social environment

Components of Social Case work

The nucleus of social case work is given by H.H. Perlman which is, 'a person with a problem comes to a place where a professional representative helps him by a given process'. This entire phenomenon is also known as the 4P's and is used in most of the situations where a person seeks professional help. There are four components of casework known as the 4 P's:

1. The person: The person is any individual who is under stress or is facing problem in his/her life. The person can be a man, woman or a child. The person in social work terminology is called the 'client'. The person may have problem due to his/her inability of adjusting to the existing situation which is created by forces which are beyond his/her control. This problem can be social, economic or psychological in nature. When confronted by a problem, an individual usually tries to solve the problem by

employing solutions from his/her previous experiences. However, when the problem does not seem to resolve, an external support is needed and then the individual seeks for professional help. A person becomes a 'client' as soon as he starts getting professional help.

2. The problem: A problem is an obstacle or a hindrance in the normal functioning of an individual. Problems usually arise due to unmet needs, maladjustments and frustrations. When these unmet needs or frustrations prolong for a longer period of time and start affecting the social functioning of an individual, they take shape of problems. Thus, intrapersonal problems arise due to unmet needs and desires of the person, which affect the person's living situation or the effectiveness of his/her efforts to deal with it.

3. The place: 'The place' is a social service agency or a social service department where the person comes for help with his/her problem. Place may include a larger institution (e.g., the local authority), or the smaller social work microcosm (e.g., the psychiatric social work department in a mental hospital). Place may also include the institutions in which caseworkers' practice (schools, child guidance clinics, children's departments of the hospitals and courts and so on).

4. The process: A process, is a number of stages or steps followed by the case worker to help the client. It is mandatory for a professional worker to follow certain steps in order to help the client. The worker is required to maintain a good rapport with the client throughout the process. The worker helps the client to strengthen his/her coping mechanism in a problematic situation. The professional social worker accepts the client, develops a good relationship with client and tries to elicit facts. The facts stated by the client are properly diagnosed and the worker helps the client to arrive at the solution, ensuring full participation of the client in the process.

Principles of Social Casework

The principles of social casework are applied in establishing close relationship between social caseworker and the client. Relationship is the medium through which changes are brought in the behaviour and personality of the client. The term relationship in social casework was used for the first time by Miss Virginia Robinson in her book, "A Changing Psychology in Social Case Work" in 1939. The social casework relationship is the dynamic interaction of attitudes and emotions between the social caseworker and the client with the purpose of helping the client to achieve a better adjustment between himself and his/her environment. Thus the purpose of establishing relationship is to help the client with his/her psychosocial needs and problems. The relationship between

caseworker and client may be more strengthened by using certain principles. These principles are:

1) Principle of individualization: No two persons are alike in all qualities and traits. Their problems may be the same but the cause of the problem, the perception towards the problem and ego strength differs in every individual. Therefore, each individual client should be treated as a separate entity and complete information is required to establish close relations in order to solve his/her problem from root.

2) Principle of meaningful relationship: The purpose of establishing relationship in social casework is to change the behaviour of the client or to achieve adjustment in maladjusted situation. Meaningful relationship is developed in social casework by demonstrating the interests in client. He/she is convinced of the caseworker's warmth as an individual and conveys respect and caring for him/her. In return, the caseworker helps the client to trust in his/her objectivity and feel secured as worthwhile individual.

3) Principle of acceptance: Social caseworker accepts the client as he is and with all his/her limitations. He/she believes that acceptance is the crux of all help. It embraces two basic ideas --- one negative and one positive. He/she does not condemn or feel hostile towards a client because his/her behaviour differs from the approved one. Later on, he/she tries to modify his/her behaviour step by step.

4) Principle of communication: is a two-way process. There must be proper communication between caseworker and the client, which helps, in proper understanding of each other. It is the road to the identification of the client's problem. The function of social caseworker is primarily to create an environment in which the client will feel comfortable in giving expression to his/her feelings. It depends on a proper communication.

5) Principle of expression of feelings: Purposeful expression of feelings is the recognition of the client's need to express his/her feelings freely, especially his/her negative feelings. The caseworker listens purposefully, neither discouraging nor condemning the expression of those feelings. Sometimes he/she even stimulates and encourages them when the expression is of therapeutic nature.

6) The Principle of controlled emotional involvement: The social caseworker tries to understand the client's feelings and emotions but he/she himself/herself does not involved emotionally in his/her problems.

7) Principle of non-judgmental attitude: The non-judgmental attitude is a quality of the casework relationship. The caseworker does not blame the client for his/her problem nor he assigns any responsibility for his/her miseries. He/she only

evaluates the attitudes, standards or action of the client.

8) Principle of client self-determination: The client's self-determination is the practical recognition of the right and need of clients to freedom in making his/her own choices and decisions. But this right is limited by the client's capacity for positive and constructive decision making.

9) Principle of self-awareness: It means that caseworker should know his/her own strengths and limitations in dealing with client's problems. If he/she feels that the problems of the client is beyond his/her capacity, the client should be transferred to the appropriate authority.

10) Principle of social functioning: Social functioning means the functioning of the individual in his/her social roles and relationships, with emphasis on his/her relation to the environment. The caseworker tries to assess the roles of the client and his/her capacity to perform these roles.

11) Principle of tuning behaviour: Man has body, mind and intellect as three instruments of experiences through which life constantly pulsates. These three instruments have their own distinct characteristics in each person. Hence each person has unique personality. There is need of tuning three instruments for right perception and thinking. The social caseworker does it.

12) Principle of social learning: Social learning is a pre-requisite to the changes that are inevitably involved in problem-solving. The social learning processes involves (1) arousing and focusing attention and concern, (2) organising and evaluating the problem and planning future action, (3) searching for and acquiring new information, (4) providing opportunities to the client for new experience.

13) Principle of confidentiality: confidentiality is the preservation of the secret information concerning the client, which is disclosed in the professional relationship only.

Conclusion:

Many writers and professionals have contributed their understanding and technical perspective on social casework. Perlman concluded that it is a process of four components that are related to one another. In this process, the problems of individuals are well addressed. According to Perlman, a person comes with a problem to a place and a social caseworker helps him/her with though a well-defined process. On this note, the casework is understood as the method of social work to help an individual to solve their problem and helping them to cope effectively in the social functioning process.

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